

THE FUTURE OF MASS TRANSIT OPERATIONS IN NIGERIA

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INTRODUCTION

Over the years, transport has played an important role in the growth, development and sustainability of various national economies. It is an agent of growth, change and development in every sector of an economy. As an agent of change, it has brought about significant transformations in every sphere of human existence, be it social, economic, political, recreational, religious, cultural geographical and even in the distribution of information to all economic of scale. It also helps in the mobilization of all factors of production and trade and all commercial and geographical activities of nations (Ndikom, 2006)

Ideally, the economic development of a developing nation such as Nigeria should reflect in the development of its transport system. This is because transport serves as the life wire of any nation's economy: hence, the formulation or execution of policies that disrupt the efficient running of the transport system will definitely affect the efficiency and well-being of the society as well as the people.

Transport services are the arteries for the “flow” of people information, raw materials and finished products/services which build and main society. The significance of transport is anchored on the inherent ability to overcome space, where by passengers and goods are moved from one place to another in order to achieve social economic, political and psychological aspirations in an unhindered manner (Ndikom, 2004). A developed transport system is the hall mark and symbol of a developed society, hence, a nation can be said to have attained a given level of growth and development by the nature of its transport system. (Ndikom, 2006)

This also accounts for why countries, such as Nigeria cannot be described as developed. This is because; the economic development of any society is a complex process which depends on several interacting forces. Today in Nigeria, there is widespread concern for transport planning, with the desire to promote rapid economic development. Despite the efforts by successive administrations, over the years, to invest in road, public transport and other sub-sector of the transport industry, there has not been any evidence of appreciable improvements in the sub-sector. This is particularly true of road transport, which is by far the most widely used mode of transport in Nigeria.

Of all commodity movements to and from seaports, at least two thirds are now handled by road transport, while up to 90% of all other internal movement of goods and persons takes place by road (Onakamaiya, 1980). It is therefore expected that the policies and priorities of the governmental would in principle be reflected in the pattern of resource allocation for the road transport sub-sector. Since the beginning of the 20th century, Nigeria has passed through various forms of colonial and past colonial administration, each with its non-vested interest and bias for different modes of transport. Although various development programmes have been implemented on the basis of some official guidelines or principles of road transport development, it is doubtful that there is any definite comprehensive national policy in place for all the sub-sector of the transport industry in Nigeria (Ndikom, 2006). Since Nigeria independence in 1960, the major focus in policy matters relating to the transport sector has been geared towards ensuring adequate movement of passengers and goods, thereby ignoring the importance of freight movement within the country.

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GOVERNMENT POLICY PROBLEM AND IN ACTION

Ever, since our independence in 1960 and the eventual takeover of the reins of power from the Colonial masters, the transportation industry has suffered from government policy inconsistencies and lack of proper and operational funding, which over the years had affected the operationalization of this sector of the economy, no matter whichever mode that in involved (Ndikom, 2008). It is pertinent to note that one important observation during the fourth national development plan (1981-1985) was that allocation to the transport sector rose to N 10. 7 billion from 309 million in the 1962 – 1968 development plan. This was an increase of 3,365 percent in fewer 25 years (Filani, 1991). The figures show that for the first two and half decades after Nigeria's independence, the transport sector had an average share of 20.3 percent of the total national resource outlay. These ever suggest that of every naira of planned expenditure in Nigeria development effort since 1960, about 20 naira has been spent on the transport sector. With such massive investment in the nations transport sector, there had not been any significant physical results and achievements recorded in the areas of different modes of transport which are road, rail, water ways, air, and pipe line. Despite these little achievements made by government however, the transport sector is known to be seriously handicapped by many problems ever since which still persist till today.

Such problems are identified by Filani (1986, 1991), Bolade (1991) and Ikya(1996) includes

1. Inadequate planning
2. Lack of inter-modal coordination
3. Insufficient public transport to cope with ever-increasing demand urban traffic congestion
4. Neglect of rural to rural urban transport
5. The problem of mobility (Both of freight and people) in the country and particularly overland freight which is the issues concerning management of rail as a future anchor for public transport operations in Nigeria

Inspite of the fact that government has always given the transport sector priority in all the successive development plans, the transport situation in Nigeria is nevertheless getting worse, there is yet on clearly articulated transport policy for transport development in Nigeria, most of the current polices impinging on the transport sector exhibit many inconsistencies and lack of clearly defined and stated objective. Transport programmes have, at best, been have, at best been piece-meal and uncoordinated with implementation being haphazard and disjointed. The awareness of this problem made the military administration in 1985 under the leadership of General Jeremiah Useni to formulate a comprehensive transport policy as a blue print for the development of the nation's transport policy as a blue print for the development of the nation's transport sector. Two years after setting up the machinery for the formulation of the policy, only the draft of a national transport policy for Nigeria – moving out of crisis-emerged.

Meanwhile, the transport crisis continues unabated. The draft national transport policy recognizes that Nigeria is experiencing an explosive urban growth, which results in overstressed the scarce urban infrastructure, hence, the resolve by government to provide adequate and efficient transport system to enable the national economy function well (Adeniji, 1991). Up till today, there has never been any feasible transport policy in place, despite this recent efforts government made to assemble stakeholders in the transportation sector in Kaduna last August 2010 to review the draft policy on transportation is still left in the hands of this present national assembly for ratification, confirmation and passage into bill for possible implementation. My worry is that, there are some critical areas that were not eventually covered that will address the cogent issues in the public transport sector of the economy. There is also an obvious missing gap in the emerging of the transport policy which is the acceptance and obvious entrenchment of operationalization of the concept of para transit modes as public transport in our constitution rather than these discarded tunes by states government.

PUBLIC TRANSPORT -CONCEPT OF PARA -TRANSIT MODES

Para transit modes are an integrating part of a public transport system; they are part of the unconventional modes of public transport. But in Nigeria, it is often taken to mean a public transport system. This misrepresentation is largely due to the lack of knowledge of the rudimentary aspect of the science of transport, as a profession and discipline (Ndikom, 2006). This misrepresentation is a testimony to the fact that public transport has been greatly ignored by the various successive governments in Nigeria, a growing and developing nation. In the process of

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achieving physical interaction, transport becomes highly indispensable; thereby justify the assertion of Munby (1968) that, there is no escape from transport. Although, para-transit mode are part of the public transport system, the two concept cannot be used interchangeably. A para-transit mode is more anchored on the method of operation and service delivery than on the modes are known as intermediate modes of transport for transporting a few number of persons from an origin where they are not relatively valued much and important to a destination where their relative economic importance are greater. Therefore an 18 or 14 seater bus is not a mass transit or public transport bus, but a para-transit mode of transport. There is need for Nigeria (as a government entity including federating states) and Nigerians to actually understand the full operationalization of the public transport mode and that of para-transit modes as they are not the same in terms of operations and services, but they evenly complement each other in actualizing the demand-supply needs of the movement of people at any given point in time. The sooner the concept of para-transit modes is understood by the public as a complimentary mode of public transport the better for us as a developing nation. (Ndikom, 2008).

It is obviously true that the situation in Nigeria today regarding the non-adoption of public transport mode as an official means of transport, as a developing nation, worsening road situation and obvious lack of an enduring transport policy initiation and implementation, has called for the need to use para-transit modes as the major transport modes in the country. Despite that, Nigeria is currently experiencing rapid urbanization, with its adverse effects on urban mobility. In the absence of conventional public transport modes, para-transit modes of operations dominate the urban transport scene. (Ndikom, 2008). Until the turn of the 21st century, the majority of Africans lived in villages and small towns, where residents only needed to travel a few kilometers to obtain the needed goods and services. However, with increasing urbanization and motorization and the resultant spatial differentiation and expansion, these practices no longer hold. The numbers of real or assumed needs and wants have multiplied markedly, and these have greatly increased the need to commute between and within settlements of differing size (Adeniji, 1987). Evidence has shown that, owing to the diversity of travel patterns, user preferences, ridership densities and land use, and the affordability and availability of private and public transit, a single mode of public transport cannot serve all the inter and intra-settlement transport needs in Nigeria.

Until now, Nigeria policy-makers and transport planners tended to concentrate on private and conventional public transport modes in seeking a solution to the increasing accessibility and mobility problems (Adeniji, 1987). However, for various socioeconomic reasons, the majority of Nigerian still do not own/have access to private transport and the attempts at providing conventional modes of transport continue to dominate the transport market (Ndikom, 2008)

MANAGEMENT AND OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT IN NIGERIA

Over the years, the management of the Nigerian public service organizations or corporations has been a daunting task, complex and largely inefficient reflecting high level of incompetence. Therefore, the management of the Nigerian railways as a corporation has been largely inefficient, over the years and the corporation's infrastructure has been largely inadequate and non-functional. The Nigerian railways system has suffered so many managerial problems ranging from government lack of funding, undue interference, control and policy inconsistencies over the years. The Federal Urban Mass Transit as a child of circumstance in those days, suffered the same feats which wasn't the best and that had caused both corporations to virtually come to a standstill, regardless the ever increasing trend or urbanization in most of our cities. This near-collapse status is however, also due to the system's inability to cope with the competition from road and allied haulage industry at the end. There is need therefore to overhaul the entire system and give it a new operational outfit, in terms of efficiency and productivity.

The rail transport system in Nigeria today has been fully managed as a public corporation, with little or no positive effect on performance and improved operational capacity. The worsening situation is that the track lines that were constructed at the beginning of the 19th century have not been replaced, are not maintained, and there are much more dilapidated infrastructure which is the main problem of the corporation even today. Obviously, no much effort has been made towards improving these infrastructures that are now over a century old. To a large extent, this is the sign of a sick and decaying corporation, without these improvements in terms of efficiency and effectiveness in line with international standards and best practices. The Nigeria railway system

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has been run under civil service structures and modalities, which makes the case peculiar to Nigeria. There is need to reform the entire system if we must achieve a viable public transport system and also to reposition it at the level of international standard, best practices and prepare it for effective internal competition (especially that from the road sector). The Nigerian railway system thus has some inhibiting factors, with regards to operational performance and productivity and the government over the years has not helped matters but rather paid lip service to issues concerning its growth and development (Ndikom, 2008).

Despite the immense socio-economic benefits of rail transport and the recent attempts at revamping the Nigerian railways corporation (NRC), the corporation seemed to be eternally trapped in a vicious circle of poor operating problem and poor financial status (Adesanya, 2002). Infact, by the mid-1990s and even now, the Nigerian Railways Corporation or the railway system was said to be moribund, as it was at its worst level of decay in terms of managerial excellence, operational performance and productivity (Ndikom, 2008)

Under the federal urban mass Transit Administration, the issue of management, operational performance, organization and control of events and unfolding challenges was nothing to write home about. I must admit here and again that, the organizational structure, managerial competences and control initiative as at the time of its establishment was very high. There were high hopes and good expectations due largely to the quality of management injected within the system. This was short-lived as hopes were dashed and expectations became a mirage at the end of the day due to government undue intervention, influence, policy inconsistency and lack of funding for the parastatal. Ever since then, this has affected the operationalization of public transport in Nigeria, inspite of some of the appreciative efforts made by private sector. (Ndikom, 2008),

GOVERNMENT RECENT EFFORTS ON PUBLIC TRANSPORT IN NIGERIA

The ever increasing trend of rural-urban migration culminating into a stressed like urban centres in most cities in Nigeria have indeed called for a need of an enduring public transport system in Nigeria. Obviously, the inability of the state in not adopting an enduring public transport scheme in Nigeria, which is due largely to political reasons over the years, gave rise to the emergence of commercial motorcycling called Okada, taxis and small shuttle 18 seater buses to take centre stage in usurping the responsibilities of a well-managed public transport system in Nigeria. Interestingly, recent efforts of some state governments on initiating and also the adoption of public transport schemes in their respective states are commendable hope raising and a sign of good things to come. The introduction of a BRT public transport buses by Lagos state government and also the adoption of public transport buses by some local government in Lagos are something worth commending as a good effort. Obviously, some of the states government which have taking the lead in adopting an operational public transport scheme using one form of para-transit means in the southwest, south east, south south, Abuja, in the north have tried to reduce urban-transit stress, structural inefficiency, some level of unemployment, and infrastructural decay within the operationalization of the public system. (Ndikom, 2008)

To a large extent, it has in a way reduced some level of urban traffic congestion and increased infrastructural facilities that have handled the incidence of urbanization problems in most of these states like Abuja, Lagos, Port Harcourt and Kano to say a few. The unfolding events in Nigeria as regards increasing rate of urbanization and the attendant issue of the non-adoption of public transport modes, as a means of transport is the dominance and usage of intermediate modes of inter-settlements and usage of intermediate modes of inter-settlements in Nigeria. However, their role is more important in inter-settlement journeys where they dominated the public transport market. With the exception of a few luxury bus services provided by some state owned public transport establishment (Mostly in form of para-transit mode except Lagos state), and a handful of private operations the various intermediate modes of public transport are the prime transporters of goods, services and passengers on inter-settlement roads. Vehicles use includes adapted one like molue, boleka, many wagon, and mini buses, pick up vans and motorcycles, bicycle and beast of burden typifying the non-motorized modes used for inter-settlement journeys. One important features of intermediate public transport in Nigeria is the virtual private car ownership (Ndikom, 2008). Obviously, another disturbing issue in public transport management and control is the unregulated control measures of easy entry and exist within the intermediate mode market. The issue of raising wave of unemployment trend in Nigeria labour market mostly the graduate youths, has led most government in providing mini taxi cabs and motor cycles to these youth as a way of reaching out and solving the

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problem of unemployment, some state like Lagos, Oyo, Imo, Port Harcourt, Ondo, Enugu states, and many others etc, have taking the lead in this regard. These over the years has helped in reducing unemployment as most of these cars are given to them on hire purchase basis, hence reducing also the public transport needs and enhanced transport efficiency with its sporadic traffic congestion.

It is important to note that road based transport modes account for about 90% of the overall transport demand and traffic in Nigeria, hence the contribution of intermediate public transport modes in a developing economy like Nigeria cannot be underestimated (Adeniji, 1987). It is relevant to note that, in a few urban cities and centres such as Lagos, Kano, Kaduna, Owerri, Port Harcourt, Enugu, Calabar, until recently Benin City, some of the public transport systems are municipalized. In most cases, however, the use of municipal buses are so few that, they are only symbolic in nature and operational modalities are not in tandem with modern public transport trends world over. On this note, it is needful at this stage for government to have a comprehensive review of public transport policy in this era when there are attempt to enact a national transport policy in this era. Where there are attempts to enact a national transport policy with the inclusion of para-transit modes (Okada and taxi cabs) as an acceptable mode of operation of our public transport schemes, there is no way we shall wish away their valid and cardinal contributions in the recent growth and development of our economy as nation's state. Obviously, many other cities in the country (such as Aba, Akwa Ibom, Ibadan, Ebonyi, and Yola) have tried municipalizing bus services but have to abandon the idea, largely as a result of financial mismanagement, managerial incompetence, and unprofessional team spirit.

EMERGENCE AND RELEVANCE OF PARA-TRANSIT MODES (OKADA AND MINI CABS) IN PUBLIC TRANSPORT OPERATION IN NIGERIA

The true transport situation in Nigeria and the non-adoption of a conventional public transport mode have indeed called for the need to use para-transit modes, as a major transport mode in the country. Nigeria is currently experiencing rapid urbanization in most of her cities, with its adverse effect on urban mobility. In the absence of true conventional public transport modes due largely to its non-adoption policy by government in Nigeria, has elicited para the transit operations to dominate the urban transport scene. In recent years, urban mobility (intra-city movement) in Nigeria has witnessed new dimensions (trends) that have been amply replicated in other contemporary urban centres across many West African countries such new dimensions in intra-urban city movement manifested in the emergence of motorcycles, known as Okada in Nigeria palace, for public transport. The steady decline in the level of motorization nationwide for over a decade (around 1988 – 1999), during which fleets of motor vehicles decreased drastically, and the acute shortage of supplies in transport services, relative to the increasing mobility demand, necessitated the need to the use of motorcycles for commercial purpose of Nigeria. Infact, there was an influx of used (or called tokunbo) motorcycle into Nigeria, for use as public transport vehicles in cities such as Ibadan and Lagos, since the late 1980s. However, motorcycles were part of the vehicular fleets in these cities until recently, when they were adopted for public commercial transport purposes. The upsurge in the fleet of commercial motorcycle between 2000 and 2004 is a clear testimony of the increasing demands for this mode of intra-city public transport (Ndikom, 2008)

Consequently, commercial motorcycles are now considered by many as the most effective means of commercial transport in major cities in Nigeria. Commercial motorcyclists are known for penetrating the nooks and crannies of towns even through routes which are not accessible to taxis and buses, and they offer door to door services. Of course, it is remarkable to note that motorcycles are relatively faster means of transport especially in short-distance trips.

This trend in urban mobility has significantly reduced waiting time and other forms of hardship encountered by commuters in the process of gathering public transport, including the ability to get to one's destination at record time. Infact, the contribution of commercial motorcycle to the growth and development of public transport in Nigeria cannot be underestimated. The rate at which they offer services is unparalleled (Ndikom, 2008). Moreso, the role of commercial motorcycle (Okada) in today's Nigeria is to compliment the services of other para-transit mode of transport, in moving passengers and goods from one point to another. And okada had played well this role for many years, albeit, with the consequences of serious health hazards to the society. But, it is noteworthy that, despite its various harm to the society, okada has come to stay as a viable mode of public transport in

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Nigerian rural and urban setting. This is because, it has been used as a means of employment generation by a good number of the youths who do not undergo any training before they embark on the business (Ndikom, 2008).

This sort of trend has presented a very ugly scenario, as the number of road traffic accidents has increased dramatically due to the activities of commercial motorcyclists. Regrettably, even though the ugly situation has forced the Nigerian state to adopt these form of para-transit modes as part of her public transport mode, the issue of menace and other vices from the commercial motorcycles and minibuses began to have it toll on our natural traffic control system and negative economic effects in particular. The issues of one chance syndrome and motorcycle theft system were on the increase in most cities of the nation. The number of accident victims on our hospital due to reckless driving of most untrained drivers of these commercial motorcyclist and minibus driver were becoming uncontrolled. Most state governments and the federal government became worried on the ever increasing level of accident victims on our roads and also the rate of crimes and other related vices were on the increase in most cities in Nigeria. Obviously, some state governments like lagos, Cross River, Kano, Abia, Imo, and Abuja started to regulate the period from 6 am to 7 pm daily (Ndikom, 2008). Also, most state governments banned the use of commercial motorcycles in the state capital and environs of which Abuja and Owerri and others took the lead to ban Okada use and minibus operations in some state capitals (Punch, 2008).

These actions have some meaningful effects on the operational economy of the states (Ndikom, 2007). Also, non-motorized modes such as bicycles and beast of burden are used in some settlement. Bicycles are very common in the middle belt and southern parts of the country. In most settlements in the northern states of the country, bicycles are hired out to members of the public in a similar manner to car hire services found in Europe and North America (Ndikom, 2008)

THE FUTURE OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT: THE RAIL INITIATIVE AND REFORMS

Of all modes of overland transport in Nigeria, rail transport has perhaps the greatest carrying capacity. In other words, the rail system has the ability to move bulky or huge tonnage of goods and a mass of passengers relatively cheaply, especially if haulage over long distance is involved. The railways have to the capability of impacting tremendously on the spatial and economic growth of settlements, regions and countries (Adesanya, 2002). The Nigerian, railways, has come a long ways since 1898, and has contributed immensely to both inter-regional and international trade, as well as in the movement of passengers. The contribution of rail transport to the movement of passengers and goods has been highly significant (Adesanya, 1998). This fact is underscored by the immense carrying capacity of the rail transport, especially in moving bulky goods and a mass of passengers relatively cheaply over long distances. The Nigerian railways during the hay days made substantial contributions to the Nigerian economy. Rail transport can contribute to the administration of territories creation of employment opportunities, promotion of trade and commerce, enhancement of internal cohesion, facilitation of urban development and the movement of military troops, as well as generation of revenue to government (Ndikom, 2008).

As a mode of transport, and also a critical component of a public transport system, rail transport is an essential component within the transport system spectrum. It can actually be classified as an overland transport, relying on the use of specific infrastructure to qualify as rail transport. The ever increasing trend of urbanization in most of our urban cities, has been having its toll on the efficiency and effectiveness of urban mobility, which necessitated the need to resuscitate the Nigerian railways as a potent and possible future public transport mode in Nigeria. The dilapidation of most urban infrastructure and chocking levels of use due largely to the problem and effect of urbanization and urban mobility made it imperative to anchor our future hopes on public transport mobility in most of these major cities on rail transport system. This is because the increasing issues of motorization and influx of private car ownership in most major cities have over the years complicated the worsening and chocking urban traffic congestion and the present situation in most of these cities is far near no solution strategy, even in the face and introduction of BRT and private sector luxury bus public transport operational services in Lagos State.

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The increasing trend in breeding high level of unproductive workforce due to the hours spent in these daily traffic jams and situation in Lagos, Kano, Abuja, Port Harcourt and even Owerri, is really becoming worrisome and calls for an urgent solution and government intervention if we must progress in lifting and emancipation of our present economic woos from the valley and key into the objective of the vision of 20, 2020. Sadly enough, the initiation and introduction of BRT buses in Lagos by the government and personal private efforts and even that of some local government initiatives in launching luxury bus services, have not helped in any way to Lagos state. Hopefully, the present effort of Lagos state government in trying to resuscitate the metro-lines (Rail ways lines) which was once an abandoned project in Sir Jankande's administration is a welcome development. The cost of developmental wastages of this critical and cardinal national infrastructure in terms of prominent buildings giving way from the proposal routes (from Ijora-Orile, Mile two-Badagry axis) should not short sight the policy anchors of the huge benefits this singular project can offer in the entire transformation of Lagos state and reduce traffic congestion in the state also. The recent efforts of the Nigerian Railways corporation in resuscitating rail public transport passenger services in Lagos is a welcome development and good things to come. This is because, the traffic chaotic situation in Lagos will soon disappear from Lagos streets and roads which the BRT buses even with special routes and dedicated road lanes have not done over these past three years of the introduction. The FCT government efforts in ensuring the establishment of a possible rail transport services in Abuja and environs are commendable and welcome development in this time and age of our development.

This is because rail transport services are one of the known public transport mode that can transform the operational efficiency and economic survival of any nation, be it developed and developing state. (Ndikom, 2010). This is because without rail, it will be difficult to achieve a well-articulated and sustainable public transport mode in a developing and Nigerian stressed-like economy (Ndikom, 2009). There is need for the other states to follow the Lagos State initiatives. In some Nigeria urban centres, the potential for passenger railway services exist. Such urban centres include Lagos, Ibadan, Enugu, Kano, Kaduna, and Port Harcourt. However, it is only in Lagos that this potential has been partially exploited until lately when the FUMTP initiative culminated in the commencement of such services in Ibadan metropolis which is good and commendable.

PUBLIC TRANSPORT FUTURE: FERRY PASSENGERS SERVICE INITIATIVES: - The ever increasing trend of incidental rate of urbanization problems with the attendant problems of increased rate of urbanization problems with its attendant problems of increased traffic jams motorization, infrastructural decay and uncontrolled accidental injuries etc, has necessitated the urgent need to introduce ferry passenger services in all the state that has some form of canals or river for such services. The ferry passenger services is one of the most urban transport services operated by the public sector based on ferries, which over the years, have provided some skeletal services in Lagos and to lesser extent in Port Harcourt. Obviously, most of the state government ferry services are inter-settlement in nature. The inland waterways department of the federal ministry of transport and the Lagos state ferry services provide these services in Lagos Metropolis. Ferry terminal are located at the Marina, Apapa, Wharf, Oyingbo, Ikoyi, Maroko, Victoria Island, Mile 2 and Tarqua bay etc. Workers use these ferry services during the peak periods on weekdays, while they are mostly used for recreational purpose on weekends. The ridership has been increasing since 1988 with increasing trend of city traffic problems/jams when it rose from 690,000 to a little under one million in 1990. Sadly though revenue from the relatively low fares does not cover the cost of operations; hence the ferry services are operating at a loss (Adeniji, 1986). There is need to resuscitate the use of ferry transport services in all states in Nigeria that are linked with water, through the dredging of inland waterways due largely from the sudden rise in the trend of urban mobility, as traffic jams in big cities (in Lagos, port Harcourt, Warri etc) seem to discourage the use of personal cars, ease off tension, increase manpower productivity at work place, create more employment opportunities and increase the state revenue base through taxable adults engaged in employment within the operations of the emerging public transport system in most states like Lagos, Port Harcourt, Lokoja etc.

PRIVATE SECTOR PARTICIPATION AND INITIATIVES

Over the years, the private sector participation in public transport operations dates back in the days of early 1960's with the use of Bolekaja and other forms of adapted and articulated vehicles. In the early 1970s, it moved from that to the introduction of luxury buses usually imported from Brazil by likes of Ekene Diri Chuwku

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Transport, Orientals Transport. Today bus luxury operation has been intensified through the likes of likes of Ifesinachi Motors, the Young Shall Grow Motors and the ABC Transport Plc. This has played significant contributions in both city and long distance inter-state a travel that has also transformed the operationalization of our economic system. Also, the private sector intermediate or para-transit operations are ubiquitous in Nigerian urban centres where they still provide between seventy and ninety percent of public transport services. Like their counterparts in other developing countries, these operators who provide a wide variety of services ranging from taxis, mini buses to adapt to buses are demand responsive. In most urban centres in Nigeria, with exception of Lagos, molue and mini buses operate flexible route schedules, whereas the government undertakings operators fixed route (LSTC) Usually, during the peak periods they concentrate their services along high demand and routes and as a rule do not operate on uneconomic routes where government operations are often compelled to provide social services at relatively cheaper fares (Adeniji, 1986) it is often seen that the intermediate modes of public transport lacks quality control, which affects three following areas:

- i. There are no official entry control restrictions into the urban public transport market especially the number of vehicles allowed to operate
- ii. There are no restrictions on service standards with regards to the types of services to be allowed; vehicles standards, including types condition of the vehicles; passenger capacity; and driver standards that is satisfactory minimum age requirements
- iii. Fares charged, with regards to the reasonableness of fares: and the absence of a fare structure of fare tariffs which will be made know to members of the public to avoid the present exploitation by most operations of intermediate public transport

The issue of absence of quality control in these areas has given rise to numerous problems associated with the planning, operation and management of urban intermediate public transport system in this country. Such problems include

- i. Unreliable services
- ii. Poorly maintained and overcrowded vehicles
- iii. Bad drivers (and a high number of road accidents)
- iv. Proliferation of one man operators with high turnover rates
- v. Exploitative fares and charges

In spite of these problems however, urban users of intermediate services have to put up with them given the critical shortage in the supply of urban transport services vis-à-vis the demand for such services. The problem of high vehicle costs and spare parts that affect government operators mentioned earlier is the most critical one now threatening the continued existence of intermediate urban transport operations in Nigerian. If the present trend in the attrition of their vehicles continues, and individual operators generally cannot replaces it at a comparative rate, in the next few years the urban mobility crisis will pose incalculable threats to the socio-economic and political efficiency and overall survival of our urban centres (Ndikom, 2008)

STRUCTURAL REFORMS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT OPERATIONS IN NIGERIA: The obvious lack of an enduring public transport policy in place by government over these years has complicated the more, the urban city traffic problems and a possible buildup and development of urban city. Infrastructure in place. These problems have further worsened by daily increase of urbanization problems as regards to urban mobility. The overstretched urban infrastructures and facilities due to recent up-surge in urbanization in urban mobility, there is serious need to have a review in the structural reforms of urban public transportation polices to really cope with the issues of urban traffic problems. There is need also for the new expected transport policy to inculcate the issues of the use of para-transit modes (Okada, taxis and mini bus operations) as a consolidated part of an enduring urban public transport operations in this time and that the chaotic traffic problems is reducing the entire efficiency and productivity of these cities to zero performance.

Mostly big cities like Lagos, Kano, Port Harcourt, Enugu, Owerri, Benin, Kaduna etc. This recent attitude of some states governments in trying to ban the use of okada services in states capital isn't the right thing to do when there is no possible alternative and solutions to traffic problems in these major cities through the adoption of enduring rail transport services as our acknowledged public transport system. There is no way we can push

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away the services of Okada emergence as a means of possible public transport system in Nigeria, as it has come to stay for good, mostly in relation to door to door services offered to commuters from places of origin to places of destination at the end of the day. The more these states government find a lasting solution to these ugly trends in urban traffic problems through the introduction of a rail transport system the better. The level of traffic experienced in Owerri the state capital of Imo state, inspite of the outright ban of the use of okada transport services is nothing to write home about. The same is also found to be the experience of Lagos state inspite the BRT initiative as a major public transport system.

CONCLUSION

Public transport systems have a positive contribution to make life possible, convenient and also the well-being of urban centres in particular and all settlement in general. It is pertinent to note here that, public transport system has played a vital role in the growth and development of most urban cities of developing economics. The ever increasing trend of urban mobility due to increase in urbanization culminating into urban traffic problems, has made it necessary for the future of public transport system and operations to be built around the adoption of a possible rail transport services, ferry passenger transport services and the use of para-transport services and the use of para- transport modes (Okada mostly for the door to door services).

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